

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF STANNIC IODIDE WITH AMINES. PART I

BY SARJU PRASAD, K. N. CHATTERJEE AND M. H. RAO

Compounds of stannic iodide with primary mono- and diamines have been prepared in benzene medium and their properties studied. It has been found that 4 mols. of a primary monoamine and 2 mols. of a diamine are attached to one mol. of SnI_4 .

Persone (Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Theoretical and Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. VII, 1923) reported the formation of $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot 3\text{NH}_3$ and $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot 6\text{NH}_3$ by the action of dry ammonia on SnI_4 in CS_2 or ether, but Ephraim and Schmidt (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 3856), who used CCl_4 , obtained $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot 8\text{NH}_3$ and an unstable compound, $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot 18\text{NH}_3$.

Werner and Pfeiffer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 17, 82) prepared the compounds $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$ and $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$, by the action of aniline on the respective tin halide, which decomposed at a higher temperature.

Friedmann *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1911, 71, 97) studied the formation of the compounds $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot \text{Py}_2 \cdot 3\text{Py}$ and $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Py}$, $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{Py}$.

Heiber and Wager (*Annalen*, 1925, 444, 249) obtained the compounds $(\text{NH}_2\text{ArNH}_2)_2\text{SnX}_4$ and $[(\text{NH}_2\text{ArNH}_2)\text{SnX}_4]_2$ by the action of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-phenylenediamine on stannic halide. By the action of benzidine on SnCl_4 and SnBr_4 , he obtained the compounds $\text{SnX}_4(\text{NH}_2\text{Ar})_2$ and $\text{SnX}_4(\text{NH}_2\text{Ar})_4$ respectively and concluded that in these compounds one of the inorganic salt was linked by the subsidiary valence bonds to two nitrogen atoms.

Scaglirani (*Atti R. Acad. Lincei*, 1925, vi, 1, 582) prepared the compounds $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot 5\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ and $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot 4\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 \cdot 2\text{CHCl}_3$ in chloroform medium.

Scaglirani and Monti (*ibid.*, 1926, 4, 210) studied the action of hexamine on SnI_4 in different non-aqueous media and obtained the compounds $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$; $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 4\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{Cl}_2$; $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 \cdot \text{CHCl}_3$; $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 6\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 \cdot \text{CHCl}_3$. They concluded that according to Werner's theory of coordination there was paucity of satisfactory evidence in interpreting the formation of these compounds.

Karantshis (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1926, iv, 39, 43) prepared the compound $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot \text{NMe}_4$ by dissolving molecular proportions of SnI_4 and Me_4NI in the presence of an excess of HCl . By a similar method he prepared the corresponding compounds $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2\text{Ph}$ and $\text{SnI}_4 \cdot \text{NHC}_2\text{H}_5$, and Dimitrion (*Praktika*, 1929, 4, 140) isolated the compounds $\text{MeSnI}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$, $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$ and $\text{SnBr}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$.

It is evident that practically no work has been done on the formation of compounds of stannic iodide with amines. The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the preparation and properties of these compounds.

TABLE I

Amine-SnI ₄ compounds.	Colour.	M.P.	% Sn.		% I.		% Org. matter.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Monoamines.										
Aniline, Sn[4(C ₆ H ₇ NH ₂) ₄]	Whitish brown	150°	12.08	11.91	54.40	58.60	35.62	37.23		
<i>o</i> -Toluidine, Sn[4(C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ NH ₂) ₄]	Brown	214°	11.34	11.27	47.42	48.16	41.24	40.57	4.90	5.21
<i>m</i> -Toluidine, " "	Yellow	175°	11.60	11.27	48.25	48.16	40.15	40.57	5.02	5.31
<i>p</i> -Toluidine, " "	Yellow	180°	11.50	11.27	48.15	48.16	40.35	40.57		
α -Naphthylamine, Sn[4(C ₁₀ H ₇ NH ₂) ₄]	Yellowish brown	220°	9.93	9.91	45.40	42.37	44.66	47.72		
β -Naphthylamine, " "	Greenish yellow	214°	9.75	9.91	44.30	42.37	45.95	47.72		
<i>o</i> -Anisidine, Sn[4(CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]	Yellow	151°	10.56	10.62	45.74	45.42	43.70	43.96		
<i>p</i> -Anisidine, " "	Ash-coloured	148°	10.60	10.62	45.70	45.42	43.70	43.96		
Bethylamine, Sn[4(CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₄]	Yellow liquid	250°	13.50	12.95	54.70	55.29	31.80	31.76		
Benzylamine, Sn[4(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂) ₄]	Yellow	174°	11.26	11.28	47.99	48.16	40.75	40.56		
<i>o</i> -Phenetidine, Sn[4(C ₆ H ₄ OC ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₄]	Yellow	165°	10.34	10.13	43.05	43.23	46.61	46.64		
<i>p</i> -Phenetidine, " "	Pale yellow	164°	10.33	10.13	43.39	43.23	46.28	46.64		
Diamines.										
Ethylenediamine, Sn[2(C ₂ H ₄ NH ₂) ₂] ₄	White	158°	15.84	15.94	67.95	68.01	16.21	16.05		
Diaminidine, Sn[2(C ₆ H ₃ ONH ₂ C ₆ H ₃) ₂] ₄	Ash	195°	10.69	10.68	45.62	45.57	43.69	43.75		
<i>o</i> -Tolidine, Sn[2(C ₆ H ₃ NH ₂ C ₆ H ₃) ₂] ₄	White	198°	11.27	11.32	48.86	48.34	39.87	40.34	5.03	5.33
Naphthalenediamine, Sn[2(C ₁₀ H ₆ NH ₂) ₂] ₄	Reddish brown	160.8°	12.62	12.62	54.70	53.88	32.68	33.50		
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine, Sn[2(NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂) ₂] ₄	Pink	240°	14.37	14.09	62.24	60.27	23.39	25.64		
Benzidine, Sn[2(NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₂] ₄	Brown	182°	11.90	11.93	49.10	51.05	39.00	37.02		

All these compounds melt with decomposition.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The amine and stannic iodide used were of B.D.H. "extra pure" quality. A dilute benzene solution of the amine was added to the stannic iodide solution in benzene with constant shaking till precipitation was complete. The precipitate was filtered and washed till the washings did not produce any precipitate with stannic iodide. It was dried at the room temperature, analysed and its properties were studied. Iodine was estimated as AgI and tin as SnO₂. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method in a few cases and for the rest it was obtained by difference. The results are reported in Table I.

D I S C U S S I O N

According to Sidgwick ("Electronic Theory of Valency", 1927) the maximum covalency that tin can exhibit is 8, but usually it is 6. In all the cases studied, four molecules of monoamines and two molecules of a diamine are co-ordinated with one molecule of stannic iodide, and the maximum covalency of 8 is attained.

Almost all the compounds are semicrystalline powder with the exception of the butylamino compound, which is a liquid, having b.p. 250°. These are fairly stable in dry atmosphere, but when exposed to moist air for a long time, these absorb moisture and decompose. These are insoluble in benzene, ether, chloroform and acetone, and are readily soluble in dilute HCl, but decompose into the corresponding amine, hydroxide of tin and sodium iodide, when treated with a dilute NaOH solution.

It appears that amines attach themselves to the central atom, chelate compound being formed in the case of diamines and can be represented as Sn (4A) I₄ (where A = primary amine) and Sn (2D) I₄ (where D = diamine). The E.A.N. does not assume the inert gas configuration and therefore the compounds are not very stable.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI-5.

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